

Exploring the Causes and Effects of Farmer-Herder Conflicts in Borno State, Nigeria

¹Makinta, Maina Mohammed; ²Hamisu, Sa'adu*; ²Yusha'u Hassan

¹Department of Agriculture, Damboa Local Government, Borno state, Nigeria.

²Department of Agricultural Economics and Extension, Federal University of Agriculture Zuru, PMB 28, Zuru, Kebbi State, Nigeria.

*Corresponding author: *Hamisu, Sa'adu*

Department of Agricultural Economics and Extension, Federal University of Agriculture Zuru, PMB 28, Zuru, Kebbi State, Nigeria.

Abstract

The study focused on the causes and effects of farmer-herder conflicts in three selected Local Government Areas (Damboa, Jere, and Magumeri) of Borno State, Nigeria. A multistage sampling technique was used to select a sample size of 225 that includes farmers (150) and herders (75), respectively. A structured questionnaire and interview schedule were used to generate data for this study. Data was analysed using descriptive statistics (frequency and percentage) and Logit regression analysis. The results revealed that 51.3% and 44% of the farmers and herders were within the age bracket of 31-45 years, with the majority, 83.3% of farmers and 90.7% of herders, being male, whereby 84% of farmers and 82.7% of herders were married. Similarly, the study has revealed that the main sources of conflict between farmers and herders in the study area originated from competition over natural resources such as farmland, water, and grazing land. Whereby, destruction of farm produce and loss of animal and human lives were some of the common consequences of farmer-herder conflicts in the study area. Findings from the logit regression analysis revealed that there is a significant relationship between the socio-economic characteristics of farmer-herders and their involvement in the conflicts in the study area at the 5% and 1% levels of probability. However, the study recommended that there should be educational intervention programs as well as community development committees to curtail the occurrences of farmer-herder conflicts in the study area.

Keywords: *Farmers, Herders, Conflicts, Cause and Effects, Borno State.*

Introduction

The term 'conflict' has been variously conceptualized. However, the multiplicity of definitions has always pointed at one fact: that conflict is an enduring aspect of social existence. People believe that conflict is an inherent part of the experiences of any community of individuals. Thus, most conflicts are social in character and usually arise as human beings pursue their different survival and security needs (Onuoha, 2008).

However, in West Africa, particularly in Nigeria, there has been a considerable increase in natural resource conflict since the beginning of the 1990s (Blench and Dendo, 2005). These forms of conflict have always played a role in many parts of Nigeria, but recent conditions have led to an increase in their intensity and complexity (IITA, 2011). An area that has been of particular concern is clashes between farmers and pastoralists, especially in wetland areas (Blench and Dendo, 2005). Angaye (2003) describes such conflicts as dysfunctional, destructive, and responsible for loss of lives, properties, man-hours, investment opportunities, hunger, and starvation whenever and wherever they occur. The degree has worsened due to a number of reasons: rapid human population increase with a resultant increase of land cultivation; increased livestock population due to modern veterinary care eradicating most livestock killer diseases; lopsided government investment in agriculture giving preference to crop cultivation at the expense of other sectors; poor education of pastoralists in comparison with crop farmers; the erosion of traditional authority as a result of local government reform; and poor management of the natural resource conflicts (Daniel *et al.*, 2003, and Ishaku, 2014). There are a good

number of factors that can cause conflict between farmers and herders in Nigeria. These include land policy and regulations, encroachment of grazing reserves, encroachment of stock routes, indiscriminate bush burning, desertification, shrinkage of Lake Chad, cattle theft or rustling, and disobedience to traditional authorities (Makoye, 2012).

Borno State has recorded a number of farmer-herder conflicts in recent times with devastating consequences on lives and properties in many communities across the state. It has been reported by many authors, such as Ofouku and Isife (2009) and Odoh and Chigozie (2012), that almost all forms of violent conflicts have direct or indirect effects on crop and livestock production in the affected areas. Such effects include a reduction in output, which in turn reduces the farmers' income due to the destruction of crops and livestock. A lot of farmers and herders lost part or the whole of their crops and livestock to conflicts in different parts of the country. It is against this background that this study, therefore, focuses on the causes and effects of farmer-herder conflicts in Borno State, Nigeria.

Methodology

Borno State lies in the extreme northeastern part of Nigeria between latitudes $10^{\circ} 30'$ - $13^{\circ} 50'$ N and longitudes 11° - $13^{\circ} 45'$ E with a landmass of 69,435 km². The State shares borders with three states: Adamawa to the south, Gombe to the southwest, and Yobe to the west, as well as three countries, namely, the Republic of Niger, Chad, and Cameroon to the north, northeast, and east, respectively (Waziri, 2009). The state has a projected population of 6,450,236 people for the year 2021. The selected Local Government Areas (LGAs) have a total population of 690,516 people. That is, Damboa LGA has 276,413, Jere LGA 247,856, and Magumeri LGA 166,247 (National Bureau of Statistics, 2021).

A multistage sampling technique was used. In the first stage, three local government areas (Damboa, Jere, and Magumeri) were purposively selected based on the frequency of documented occurrence of farmer-herder conflicts from BSMAFFR (2011) and their relative peace from Boko Haram insurgency. Five villages were then purposively selected in each of the three LGAs based on the same ground, making a total of 15 villages. The villages are Abulitu, Alimiri, Iya, Kafa, and Nzuda from the Damboa Local Government Area; Dusman, Wodiya, Bwale, Kolori, and Zabarmari from Jere LGA; and Ardoram, Furam, Dongo, Ngamma, and Borno-Yesu were selected from Magumeri LGA. Ten (10) crop farmers and five (5) herders were purposively selected from each of the 15 villages. Finally, this gave a sample size of 225 respondents, that is, 150 crop farmers and 75 herders.

However, secondary data were collected from printed materials such as textbooks, journals, proceedings, theses, etc., in order to ensure the adequacy and reliability of information gathered. Whereby, primary data was collected from a structured questionnaire and interview schedule. Both descriptive and inferential statistics were used in data analysis. Descriptive statistics such as frequency distributions and percentages were used. Inferential statistics in the form of a logit regression model were used to analyse the relationship between the socio-economic characteristics of the farmers and herders and their level of involvement in the conflict in the study area. Theoretically, the model is explicitly expressed as follows:

$$Li = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \dots + \beta_{12} X_{12} + e \dots \dots \dots (i)$$

Where,

Li = Likelihood of involvement in farmer-herder conflict (dependent variable)

β_0 = intercept

$\beta_1 \dots \dots \dots \beta_7$ = estimated coefficient

X₁ = Farming Experience (years)

X₂ = Age (years)

X₃ = Income (₦)

X₄ = Family size (number of persons in household)

X₅ = Level of Education (number years spent in school)

X₆ = Farmland size (Hectares)

X₇ = Herd size (number of livestock in the herd)

Results And Discussion

Socio-economic Characteristics of the Respondents

About half (51.3%) of the farmers surveyed were between the ages of 31 and 45, whereas less than half (44%) of the herders were in the same age range, according to Table 1's results. According to this, a sizable fraction of farmers and herders were of working age and were therefore probably more capable of making decisions and acting more quickly

than their elder counterparts. Jatto (2012) asserts that farmers who are young and full of energy are particularly prone to initiating or influencing conflict.

Most of the respondents were male, consisting of 83.3% and 90.7% of the farmers and herders, respectively. The implication is that the number of women found in conflict is always far below that of the men. This may not be unconnected with the nature of socio-religious factors of the people in the study area. This agreed with the position of Mai-jir (2014), which reported that the men seem to be more dominant in most of the social and economic activities than the women, including involvement or participation in conflict.

Given that 84% of farmers and 82.7% of herders were married, the study's respondents had almost identical marital statuses, according to the findings. For farmers and herders, the percentages of divorced, widowed, and separated people were less than 7%. This suggests that the respondents were capable and accountable for fulfilling their duties while also showing greater regard for the customs and norms of their communities. This supports the findings of Jatto (2012), who found that married respondents are more likely to have some life experience since they are held to societal standards of responsibility.

According to the results, over one-third of farmers (37.4%) have families with six to ten members, while 41.3% of herders had one to five family members. The farmers are implied to have larger households than the herders. They typically marry more wives than herders, which may be due to their sedentary lifestyles; the more spouses one has, the more likely one is to produce children, and vice versa. Because of their nomadic lifestyle, which may make it inconvenient for them to take on more wives and children, the herders also maintain small families. The nomad will quickly move from one location to another once they start a dispute there. This is in line with Idris (2011), who claims that mobility the capacity of both people and cattle to relocate based on necessity is the primary tactic for herders' resilience and adaptive capacity.

Table 1 showed that roughly half of the respondents (18.2%) finished primary school, and 51.1% received Qur'anic instruction. It also showed that 9.8% of them were in secondary school. According to this, the majority of the respondents have some sort of education. Nevertheless, their educational attainment remained poor, since just 5.3% of the respondents had attended postsecondary schools, which demand additional years of study. This needs to change because it is essential to the advancement of any community. Those with less education, or illiterates, are frequently more active in conflicts than those with higher education (Mohammed, 2012).

Only 8% of farmers had farmlands larger than 11 hectares, whereas the majority (76.5%) grew crops on farmlands between 1 and 5 hectares. Agro-pastoral herders all cultivate their crops on farmland smaller than five hectares. The majority of farmers are implied to be subsistence farmers. Because subsistence farmers take every precaution to keep grazing animals from damaging their farms, areas where they predominate are more vulnerable to farmer-herder conflict.

Table 1: Socio-economic characteristics of sampled respondents

Attributes	Items	Farmers (150)		Herders (75)		Pooled (225)	
		Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq.	%
Age (years)	15-30	28	18.7	17	22.7	45	20.0
	31-45	77	51.3	33	44.0	110	48.9
	46-60	43	28.7	16	21.3	59	26.2
	61 and above	2	1.3	9	12.0	11	4.9
Mean		38		19		56	100
Sex	Male	125	83.3	68	90.7	193	58.8
	Female	25	16.7	7	9.3	32	14.2
Total						100	
Marital Status	Married	124	82.7	63	84.0	187	83.1
	Single	16	10.7	9	12.0	25	11.1
	Divorced	2	1.3	2	2.7	4	1.8
	Separated	3	2.0	1	1.3	4	1.8
	Widow	5	3.3	-	-	5	2.2
Family Size	1-5	47	31.3	31	41.3	78	34.7
	6-10	56	37.4	23	30.7	79	35.1
	11-15	15	10.0	8	9.7	23	10.2
	16-20	15	10.0	8	9.7	23	10.2
	21 and above	17	11.3	5	6.6	22	9.8

Mean		30		15		45	100
Level of Education	Primary	31	20.7	10	13.4	41	18.2
	Secondary	13	8.7	9	12.0	22	9.8
	Tertiary	7	4.6	5	6.7	12	5.3
	Adult Education	4	2.7	9	20.0	13	5.8
	Qur'anic	79	52.7	37	49.3	116	51.1
	No any education	16	10.7	5	6.7	21	9.3
							100
Farm size	1-5	114	76.5	29	100	143	80.3
	6-10	23	15.4	-	-	23	13
	11 and above	12	8.0	-	-	12	6.7
Mean		50		10		59	100
Herd size	1-25	49	76.6	7	9.3	56	40
	26-50	11	17.2	8	10.7	19	13.6
	51-100	3	4.7	42	56	45	32.1
	101-200	2	3.1	10	13.3	12	8.6
	201 and above	-	-	8	10.7	8	5.8
Mean		30		15		45	100

Source: Field survey, 2023.

Causes of Farmer-Herder Conflicts

According to the farmers' perspective, many herders seemed hesitant to monitor the movement of their animals during the grazing hours; some even let calves graze in the surrounding areas after their parents were taken for grazing, sometimes without anyone watching over them. According to Table 2, the majority of farmers (74.7%) stated that the primary reason for disputes between farmers and herders was the animals' deliberate destruction of crops. In contrast, none of the herders said that disputes between farmers and herders in the region were caused by the herders' livestock purposefully destroying crops.

This is comparable to a report by Braimah (2014) that claims that because herdsmen have knowingly and blatantly destroyed farms, causing preventable crises, they have become a serious threat to security. In the research area, the majority of herders (82.7%) said that the primary reason for disputes between farmers and herders was some farmers' unwillingness to harvest and transport their produce home on time. Furthermore, 42% of the farmers shared this viewpoint. According to the implication, these farmers' acts typically draw grazing animals to their farmlands, which could result in conflict between the two groups.

The findings also showed that 44 percent of farmers and 57.3% of herders believed that farmer-herder conflicts in the region were caused by farmers' encroachment on grazing reserves. This suggests that some farmers decrease the amount of grazing pasture accessible for cattle by growing crops on grazing lands. This is in line with Mukhtar *et al.* (2009), who state that although Borno State's pastoral system has numerous challenges, the most significant ones are livestock water scarcity, severe encroachment, instability, and, finally, a lack of veterinary care.

According to Table 2's findings, indiscriminate bush burning was cited by 40% of farmers and 36% of herders as the primary reason for disputes between farmers and herders in the research area. The truth is that some people (mostly farmers and hunters) carelessly burn the bush just after the wet seasons. When combined with high winds, fire typically results in significant harm to the impacted area, including the death of animals and the destruction of valuable trees. Conflicts between farmers and herders, as well as other groups like hunters and forest guards, might arise when the fire extends to villages.

In several states, including Adamawa, Gombe, Taraba, Yobe, and Borno, farmers burn the bush as soon as they harvest their crops to deter herders from grazing their livestock in the areas (Musa, 2013). This viewpoint was challenged by Ofouku and Isife (2009), who placed the blame on the herders. According to them, grasses and forages dry up during the dry season, and the nomads thought that new pasture would grow if the old vegetation was burned. Conflict arises between the impacted farmers and the herders as a result of the fire spreading into neighbouring farms during the herders' burning operation, destroying the crops in the fields.

Table 2: Causes of Farmer-Herder Conflicts*

Attributes	Farmers		Herders		Pooled	
	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%
Unintended damage of crop	105	70.0	56	74.7	161	71.6
Deliberate destruction of crops	112	74.7	-	-	112	49.8
Blocking of cattle corridor	45	28.7	29	38.7	72	32.0
Blocking of grazing areas	63	42.0	43	57.3	106	47.1
Blocking road to watering point	32	21.3	28	37.3	60	26.7
Dry season water source	46	42.7	18	24.0	82	36.4
Indiscriminate bush burning	60	40.00	27	36.0	87	38.7
Trimming of trees by herders	54	36.0	29	38.7	83	36.9
Trimming of trees by farmers	38	25.3	12	16.0	50	22.2
Cattle rustling/stealing	45	30.0	13	17.3	58	25.8
Delay in harvesting of farm produces	63	42.0	62	28.7	125	55.6

Source: Field survey, 2023.

NOTE: (*) Means Multiple responses

Effects of farmer-Herder Conflicts

Table 3's results showed that most farmers (66%) and herders (76%) believed that the primary outcome of disputes between farmers and herders in the study area was the destruction of agricultural products. It follows that if farmers and herders clash, the herders who are agitated tend to destroy crops, whether in the fields or in the shops. Ofuoku and Isife (2009) have demonstrated that the loss of crops was a common consequence of farmer-herder conflicts in Delta State. Ahmadu (2011) also confirmed that many deaths, crop loss, and cattle raiding were among the consequences of the hostilities in the Nigerian portion of the Lake Chad Basin.

The findings indicate that 62% of farmers and 66.7% of herders said that the primary consequence of farmer-herder conflicts in the region was the death of livestock. Furthermore, according to 49.8% of the respondents, the study area's farmer-herder disputes' most concerning consequence is the loss of human life. This stance supports numerous studies. In the communities of Alimiri, Koshifa, and Koyeri in the Damboa Local Government Area of Borno state, for example, over 30 people were killed, 8 people were maimed, and 34 animals were also slain between 2001 and 2002 alone, according to the Damboa Local Government Report (2002). Also, in the Demsa Local Government Area of Adamawa state, 28 people were feared killed, and about 2,500 farmers were displaced and rendered homeless in the hostility between cattle rearers and farmers in host communities in 2005 (Ofem and Basse, 2014).

The movement of one or both farmers and herders from the area in question is one of the most frequent causes of farmer-herder disputes in the majority of agro-pastoral environments. Borno State is not an exception, as 36% of farmers and 37.3% of herders, respectively, believed that the primary outcome of the farmers-herder disputes in the research region was forced relocation of farmers and herders. Herders were more likely to migrate since they were nomadic, which makes it easy for them to leave a place, especially if they start a fight with the farmers.

For instance, IRIN (2013) reported that local authorities expelled 700 pastoralists from Borno State in the northeast in May 2009 and some 2,000 from Plateau in April, according to local authorities. Equally, many farmers were forced to migrate in order to be free from the herders' deadly attacks.

Table 3: Effects of Farmer-Herder Conflicts*

Attributes	Farmers		Herders		Pooled	
	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%
Loss of human lives	75	50.0	37	49.3	112	49.8
Loss of livestock	93	62.0	50	66.7	143	63.6
Forced migration	54	36.0	28	37.3	82	36.4
Destruction of farm produce	99	66.0	57	76.0	156	69.3
Destruction of houses	12	8.0	9	12.0	21	9.3
Destruction of public buildings	6	4.0	2	2.7	8	3.6
Destruction of vehicles, motor cycles	14	9.3	5	6.7	19	8.4
Leads to hunger	43	28.7	17	22.7	60	26.7
Other	6	4.0	-	-	6	2.7

Source: Field survey, 2023.

NOTE: (*) Means Multiple responses

Hypothesis Testing

To ascertain the association between the socioeconomic traits of farmers and herders and their participation in farmer-herder disputes in Borno state, logit regression analysis was employed. According to the findings, family size and herd size had positive coefficients and were not significant, but education level had a negative coefficient. Farm size and income had a substantial negative correlation, although age and farming experience had a significant positive coefficient (Table 4).

A positive sign on a parameter indicated that higher values of the variable tend to increase the level of involvement in conflict between farmers and herders in the study area. Similarly, a negative value of the coefficient implied that higher values of the variable would reduce the level of involvement of the respondents in farmer-herder conflicts. Thus, farming experience, age, income, and farm size were the factors that affected the farmers' and herders' involvement in conflicts in the study area. Farm size and income had negative coefficients and were significant at 5% and 1%, respectively, while farming experience and age had positive coefficients and were significant at 5% and 1%, respectively. This contradicts the findings of Adisa (2011), which found that younger pastoralists are more likely than older ones to influence conflicts over access to pastureland. It implies that a farmer's level of conflict involvement rises with each hectare of farmland, taking into account the size of the farm.

The variables of family size, education, and herd size had no direct influence on the farmers and herders' involvement in conflicts. The P-value = 0.000 in the table indicates that there is a significant relationship between the socio-economic characteristics of the farmers and herders and their level of involvement in the farmer-herder conflicts in the study area. Hence, the null hypothesis (H₀), which says, "There is no significant relationship between socio-economic characteristics of farmers and herders and level of involvement in farmer-herder conflicts in the study area," is rejected.

Table 4: Association between Socio-economic characteristics of farmers and herders and their Involvement in farmer-herder conflicts

Variables	Coefficient	Std. Error	Z	P-value	Remarks
Constant	-3.45223	2.11965	-1.63	0.103	NS
Farming Experience (X ₁)	2.02226	1.00447	2.01	0.044	**
Age (X ₂)	0.07793	0.02846	2.74	0.006	***
Income (X ₃)	-0.80739	0.31277	-2.58	0.010	**
Family Size (X ₄)	0.01553	0.04521	0.34	0.731	NS
Level of Education (X ₅)	-0.03140	0.16151	-0.19	0.846	NS
Farm size (X ₆)	-0.17522	0.05810	-3.02	0.003	***
Herd size (X ₇)	0.31189	0.22893	1.36	0.173	NS
Log-Likelihood		-55.874			

Test that all slopes are zero: DF = 7, G = 42.786, P-Value = 0.000

Note: ***=significant at 1%, **= significant at 5%, NS=not significant

Conclusion

The study observed that competition for natural resources (grazing regions, water, and cropland) is the primary cause of disputes between farmers and herders in the study area. The farmers claimed that the primary reason for disputes with the herders was the intentional devastation of crops by the herders using their livestock. However, some farmers' unwillingness to harvest and transport their produce home on time was cited by the herders as the primary reason for the disputes. Indiscriminate bush burning and obstruction of cattle trails, grazing grounds, and routes to the watering station also contributed to conflicts between farmers and herders in the investigated region. Conflicts between farmers and herders frequently resulted in the loss of livestock and people, as well as the destruction of agricultural products.

Recommendations

The following recommendations have been put forward based on the findings of the research:

1. Educational intervention programs; including intensified agricultural extension services, nomadic education, through which the farmers and herders get information related to causes, effects and prevention of conflicts.
2. Community Development Committees are to be constituted at the community level that will ensure all the gazette grazing reserves and stock routes are free from encroachment by farmers.

References

1. Adisa, R. S. (2011). Management of Farmer-Herdsmen Conflicts in Nigeria: Implication for Collaboration between Agricultural Extension Service and Other Stakeholders. *The Journal of International Agriculture and Extension Education*, 18(1): 60-72.
2. Ahmadu, H. J. (2011). Farmer-Herder Conflict: Exploring the Causes and Management Approaches in the Lake Chad Region Nigeria. Being a Dissertation submitted in fulfillment of the Requirements for the award of Doctor of Philosophy, College of Law, Government and International Studies, University Utara Malaysia.
3. Angaye, G. R. V. (2003). Causes and cures of conflict in Nigeria: http://www.nigerdeltacongress.com/garticles/causes_and_cures_of_conflicts_in.htm Retrieved on 27th March 2013
4. Blench, R and M. Dendo (2005). Natural Resources Conflicts in North Central Nigeria; Handbook and Case Studies, No 8, Guest Road, Cambridge United Kingdom. <http://www.mandarasinfor.com/NaturalResourceConflictsNorthCentralNigeria.html>
5. Borno State Ministry of Animal Fisheries and Forestry Resources, BSMAFRR (2011). Implementation Strategies of the gazetted Grazing Reserves and Stock Routes in Borno State: a Report submitted to the Borno State Government, April 2011, Pp 7
6. Braimah, H. (2014). Fulani Herdsmen and Threat to Food Security: posted to Bendel Newspaper Company Limited Publishers of Nigerian Observers, Digital Edition. <http://www.nigerianobservernews.com/16032014/16032014/features/features4.html>
7. Damboa Local Government Report (2002). Report of 10-Man Committee on Causes, Effects and Parties Involved in Farmer-Herder Conflicts in Abulitu, Alimiri and Shettima-Abowu Villages in Damboa Local Government Area, Borno State, May, 2002. Pp 1 – 7.
8. Daniel, P., U. Hassan, M.N. Musa, H. Giwa and M. T. Hussien (2003). Farmer-herder Conflict Management and Resolution. Extended Study of Resource Use Conflict for World Bank Fadama 2 Preparations – Nigeria March, 2003.
9. Idris, A. (2011). Taking the Camel Through the Eye of a Needle: Enhancing Pastoral Resilience Through Education Policy in Kenya. *Resilience: Interdisciplinary Perspectives on Science and Humanitarianism*. 2 (12): 25-38. <http://fletcher.tufts.edu/Resilience/~media/06D3C2D2098441178487C27A2E54CF1F.pdf> Retrieved on 27th October, 2015.
10. International Institute of Tropical Agriculture, IITA, (2011): Study of Dynamics of Resource Use and Identification of Policy Gaps in Agricultural Production in southern Savannas of Northern Nigeria.
11. International Regional Information News, IRIN, (2013) Nomad Farmer Clashes Increases as Pasture Shrinks on website: <http://www.irinnews.org/Report/84761/Nigeria-Nomad-Farmer-Clashes> 22/02/2013
12. Ishaku, I. (2014). Resource use Efficiency in Yam Production in Northern Part of Benue State, Nigeria. *M.Sc Dissertation*, Department of Agricultural Economics and Extension, University of Ilorin, Nigeria.
13. Jatto, N.A. (2012). Economics and Social Characteristics of Registered Poultry Egg Producers in Ilorin, Kwara State, *Russian Journal of Agricultural and Socio-Economic Sciences* 11 (11): 18-23.
14. Mai-jir, M.M. (2014). Analysis of Contributory Factors to Conflicts among Natural Resources Users in Yunusari local Government Area of Yobe State, Nigeria. Unpublished M.Sc. Dissertation submitted to the School Post Graduate Studies, University of Maiduguri, Nigeria.
15. Makoye, K. M (2012). Drought Drives Tanzania Herders into Conflicts with Farmer, Dar es Salam
16. Mohammed, L. (2012). Federal Ministry of Agriculture and National Resources, Abuja, Nigeria. Agriculture Production, Processing and Research Priorities P7.
17. Mukhtar, A., M. Waziri and I. D. Muhammad (2009). Livestock Production in Borno State: an Overview. In Waziri, M, A. Kagu and A. K. Monguno (eds). Issues in Geography of Borno State, Volume One; published by Adamu Joji publishers, No. 123 Mangwarori street, Kano City, Nigeria.
18. Musa, A.U. (2013). Factors Inhibiting Agricultural Production among Rural Women in Southern Yobe State, Nigeria. M.Sc. Dissertation, University of Jos, Nigeria.
19. National Bureau of Statistics (2021). Annual Abstract of Statistics, Federal Republic of Nigeria: http://www.nigerianstat.gov.ng/pdfuploads/annual_abstract Retrieved on 27th February, 2021.
20. Odoh, S. I. and C. F. Chigozie (2012) climate Change and Conflict in Nigeria: A Theoretical and Empirical Examination of the Worsening Incidence of Conflicts between Fulani Herdsmen and Farmers in Northern Nigeria: *Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review*, (OMAN CHAPTER) Vol 2(1) pp. 110-124.
21. Ofem, O. O. and I. Basse (2014). Livelihood and Conflict Dimension among Crop Farmers and Fulani Herdsmen in Yakurr Region of Cross River State, *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 5(8): 512-519.
22. Ofouku, A. and B. I. Isife, (2009). Causes Effects and Resolution of Farmer Nomadic Cattle Herders Conflicts in Delta State, Nigeria: Agricultural Tropical Subtropical. *International Journal of Sociology and Anthropology* 1(2): 47-54.
23. Onuoha, F. (2008). Environmental Degradation, Livelihood and Conflicts. A Focus on the Implications of the Diminishing Water Resources of Lake Chad for North Eastern, Nigeria: *Africa Journal of Conflict Resolution*, VOL 8 (2) PP 5-61.

24. Valenti, A. D. (2015). Estimating Population at Risk in Data-Poor Environments: A Geographically Disadvantaged analysis of Boko Haram Terrorism 2009-2014: A thesis Presented to the faculty of the USC Graduate School, University of Southern California in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements for the Degree (Master of Science).
25. Waziri M. (2009). The Geography of Borno State. An overview. In Waziri, M, A. Kagu and A. K. Monguno (eds). Issues in Geography of Borno State, Volume One; published by Adamu Joji publishers, No. 123 Mangwarori street, Kano City, Nigeria.